

Leading Indigenous African Economies through Aluminium Foundry and Pot Making in Saki, Oyo State

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Abstract:

Studies on aluminium foundry and pot making among African ethnic groups, including the Yoruba in the Southwestern part of Nigeria have highlighted efforts in pottery making and aluminium goods for different utilitarian purposes. This study explores the intricate dynamics of indigenous African economies through an in-depth analysis of aluminium foundry and pot-making practices in Saki, a town located in Oyo State, renowned for its rich cultural heritage and a commercial hub for foundry products: clay and aluminium pots. This paper examined the socio-economic importance and marketability of Saki-made foundry articles with an extension of its markets beyond the shores of Nigeria. The paper employed primary and secondary sources: interviews, journal articles, books and internet sources. Historically, Saki people are acclaimed for demonstrating unusual expertise in the business compared to other towns. The business owners produce strong and durable pots of different sizes with a trademark: ‘*Saki*’, written on it, indicating identity, popularity, and wealth. These industries have significantly contributed to the local economy and provide livelihoods for numerous individuals and families, shaping the community’s identities and social structures. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of indigenous African economies and promotes socio-economic resilience and cultural continuity in contemporary African societies.

Keywords: Aluminium Foundry, Indigenous Economies, Pot Making, Commerce, Saki.

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Last week some people still called from London through WhatsApp that they wanted *Ikoko irin* and we did it for them. People from French countries also patronized us, including buyers within Nigeria such as Ibadan, Lagos, Akure, and so on. These people value Saki's pots immensely. This has enhanced and enabled Saki to be popular because Saki is always written on the pots (Mrs. Moranroola, Iron Pots Distributor/Wholeseller, Saki, 15/06/2022).

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology is a fundamental resource deployed to actualise economic growth and industrial expansion in today's globalised world (Pacey 2001). From a cultural perspective, technology refers to all that it takes (in terms of mental and material energy) for man to set in motion the natural forces of his body – his arms, legs, head, and entire body – to make natural materials available in forms that are useful to his own life. It represents all of man's efforts to influence and control nature to aid his survival as a social being, and all his attempts to solve essential but specific material and spiritual problems in life. Also, technology may be regarded as the material expression of a people's life values and attitudes, that is, culture. It represents man's ways of applying scientific knowledge to specific practical uses so that man can live more comfortably and securely today than yesterday (Andah 1992).

The concept of technology, in the words of Lawson (2008), is divided into indigenous and foreign technology. He described indigenous technology as one developed internally within a particular geographical space, while foreign technology is imported or transferred into a particular geographical space. Fusing the two above concepts, indigenous technology can be defined as developed, unique capabilities originating, or belonging to the inhabitants of a particular geographical locality. Indigenous technologies were characteristics of virtually all societies in the world before the development of advanced technologies. In this case, Nigerian societies from the precolonial era were characterised by indigenous industries that produced different articles and instruments such as clay pots, cloth weaving, textile making, hoe making, bronze casting and aluminium pot. The central focus of this study is aluminium pot making. Many other countries such as India and China have succeeded in attaining economic transformation through the exploitation of indigenous technology and resources in their domains, thereby converting local challenges into opportunities for these transformations in the process (Misa, 2003 cited in Diboye-Suku and Onuoha 2019, 14).

Nigeria is greatly blessed with gifted hands that are laboriously engaged in various types of indigenous technologies. There is hardly any part of the country that does not have remarkable indigenous technology to show for its existence. The indigenous industries, among others include the production of pots from clay and aluminium metal scraps, textile making, cloth weaving, bronze casting, leather tanning, and the like, in various parts of the country. The indigenous knowledge supporting these industries is generally passed on from generation to generation, thus making it a tradition in specific locations to produce specific products (Siyanbola, *et al*, 2012, 68). The emergence of the trade of aluminium pot (also known in Yoruba language as *Ikoko irin*) in Saki, Oke-Ogun area of Oyo State, has been traced to the post-colonial period.

This trade had been known to be of great economic importance to the town. Its socioeconomic importance because of its huge marketability cannot be overemphasized. Saki is a notable commercial hub for foundry products, especially aluminium pots. The business, according to oral evidence, began in Saki in the late 1960s. Historically, Saki people are acclaimed to demonstrate unusual expertise in the business compared to other towns in Yorubaland, who have taken it as their occupation. Both young and old are involved in the business. Adelabu and Campbell also affirmed that Saki town is well-known for its long-standing status in the artisanal production of cast aluminium cookware and a major distribution hub of aluminium cookware across the Southwestern region of Nigeria and beyond (Adelabu and Campbell 2020, 607).

The suitable nature of Saki's soil was an added advantage since the soil is used for making mould. Runge posits that casting is a type of metalworking that involves pouring molten aluminium into a mould to duplicate a desired pattern. Among the existing methods of casting, sand casting is reported as the most versatile method for producing aluminium products (Runge cited in Adelabu and Campbell 2020:608). According to R. K. Jain, moulding sand is the principal raw material used in moulding because it provides several major characteristics that may not be obtained from other materials. It is defined as granular particles resulting from the breakdown of rocks, due to the action of natural forces, such as frost, wind, rain, heat, and water currents. Moulding sand however, differs considerably in different parts of the world (Jain 2006, 148).

The compatibility of the moulding sand obtainable in Saki enhances the production of aluminium pots, compared to other places where their soil is less compatible. Thus, Saki has attracted huge economic opportunities over others through the business of aluminium pot making. The business owners produce strong and durable pots of different sizes with a trade mark, '*Saki*', written on it, sold within, and exported abroad. It is noted that aluminium pots without the inscription, Saki, stay longer in the market because people will not patronise them. A respondent from Saki said, "God used the soil to favour Saki, and that is why the business is thriving in Saki. If you produce the pots without

inscribing Saki on it, people will not purchase them from you”.ⁱ That is the reason the trade had been customized to Saki. The quality and durability of these pots are major credit to Saki artisans as many who used the pots always testified. This work is discussed under three sub-headings: markets, marketing, and patronage in Saki and beyond, aluminium pots as an indicator of Saki’s popularity, and aluminium pots making and its economic importance to Saki, with the conclusion.

2. HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE OF ALUMINIUM POT IN SAKI

In Nigeria, sand-casting or sand-cast moulding has become a widely used method of forming aluminium into products by artisans who, through a labour-intensive process, recycle scrap aluminium into a range of functional household products. Notable among these products is the cast aluminium cookware in different range, sizes and shapes. These cooking pots have become ubiquitous for both rural and urban dwellers and are used in the kitchens by the middle class and elite despite the presence of alternative products in the market. Particularly, the large-sized spherical cast aluminium pots are widely used by cooks preparing food for many people in various public spaces, including food stalls, eateries, and food processing outlets (Adelabu and Campbell 2020, 608). Recycling aluminium waste has been noted to be easier than its raw state. The energy required to melt and recycle metals is much less than the energy needed to produce them from their mineral ore. Most other materials can only be reused, whereas aluminium can be completely recovered to generate a new raw material. Recycling aluminium waste materials presents an economic advantage to the artisans (Kpelou *et al*, 2021, 148-149)

Before the colonial experience in Africa, indigenous technology was well expressed in the local system of hand manufacture of goods and implements whose basic components were wood, clay, stones, metal, textiles, and leather (Okpoko, 1999, 4). Oral tradition in Saki maintains that, unlike clay pot and weaving of cloths that had existed since the precolonial period, the making of aluminium pot making has been traced to the post-colonial era of the 1960s. It asserts that the occupation of iron pot making started in Saki after Kofi Abrefa Busia, one of the political leaders of Ghana sent Nigerians back home. Busia was a Ghanaian political leader and Prime Minister from 1969 to 1972. In the words of one respondent: “I can say that the business started in Saki in 1969 after the returnees commenced the business which they had learned in Ghana. I enrolled as an apprentice in 1969 under my boss whose name is Dauda Ajibike from Ile Iyalode (Iyalode’s Compound). I completed my apprenticeship in 1971 and I started my own business. We were not so many then. Mr Tiamiyu Ayinla was the chair of our association then.”ⁱⁱ

Consequent to the forced migration from Ghana to Nigeria, the returnees were faced with unemployment and struggle for survival. They then decided to engage in the trade they had been exposed to in Ghana, which fortunately thrived till today. Validating the pioneering role of Mr Tiamiyu Ayinla in the history of the production of aluminium pots

in Saki, he (Tiamiyu Ayinla) noted another source to Mariam Adeleke in an interview that: the history of how black people started moulding aluminium pots was dated back to when a black man worked as a cashier in an iron pots company owned by the white men in Mali. The pots being moulded were black pots, which were heavy because they were made of irons. The cashier embezzled the company's money and was dismissed and lost all entitlements.

The cashier had studied the technique the whites were using in moulding the pots with sand and melted iron. Immediately he was dismissed, he went and got sand, and instead of iron he got some aluminium scraps and got a mould to make a pot. When his previous employers saw what he came out with, they recalled him and promised to pay all his entitlements that were initially withheld. However, he rejected the offer given him to return to the company by starting his own. That was how many people went to him and became his apprentice, learning the art of moulding aluminium pots.ⁱⁱⁱ Another version from Mr Tiamiyu Ayinla of the introduction of aluminium pots in Saki states that aluminium pots started in 1969 and the art was brought into Nigeria from Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.^{iv} The assertion from some quarters, as mentioned earlier, is that it actually spread from Funtua in Northern Nigeria.

Based on the versions of origin, it can be established that aluminium pot making started in Saki in the late 1960s after the migration from Ghana, this being the most consistent version of the history elders have recounted. A retired Justice of the Federal High Court, Abuja, A.A. Kolajo, said that “*ikoko irin* is an invention in Saki. Our people who travelled to Ghana brought the idea home. Historically, Saki had nothing to do with *ikoko irin*, but it was brought, and many people started doing it, and it eventually spread to other places. I can say that they even know how to do it better than the people they got it from.”^v The practice of aluminium pot making, within a short time, was embraced in the Saki zone, and the home-based people became interested and enrolled as apprentices. Most of the initial apprentices had no formal education. Later, primary and secondary school leavers developed interest in the practice or those who lack funds to further their education. They started showing interest and enrolled as apprentices.^{vi} The practice spread from Saki to other parts of the South-West. The Saki origin of the practice was confirmed by the fact that most indigenous aluminium pots sold in Nigeria today, as mentioned earlier, are trade-marked with the word “Saki” inscribed on them, regardless of where in the region they were produced. They produced pots of different sizes and shapes to meet different cooking requirements. The sizes range from size one to size seventy, while the shape also varies (Siyanbola, *et al*, 2012, 68).

Aluminium casting is a well-established trade in the south-western part of Nigeria. It is predominant in Oyo and Osun States. As gathered in the Saki cluster (Oyo State), the first set of practitioners introduced the trade in Saki when they returned from Ghana on

repatriation in 1969. Faced with unemployment and attendant welfare problems, the returnees decided to carry on with the practice of aluminium pot casting, the technique and methodology they were exposed to in Ghana. The practice, within a short time, became so embraced in the Saki zone that the home-based people became interested and enrolled as apprentices (Siyanbola, *et al*, 2012, 68). The major raw material for Indigenous aluminium casting is processed aluminium metal obtained in the form of scraps from household utensils and other disused aluminium products. These scraps are melted in earthen furnaces and locally fabricated crucibles using firewood or palm kernel shells for fuel. Molten aluminium is poured into mud or clay moulds to form desired products. These products comprise cooking pots of various sizes. Over the years, the casting practice has evolved to the point that customised products for groups and individuals now emanate from the cluster. These generally include pots with capacities and shapes specified by customers. In that manner, customers have been a major source of innovation in the aluminium pottery cluster.^{vii}

3. METHODS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected for this research included both primary and secondary sources of historical writing. Primary data gathered through in-depth oral interviews to elicit the discourse on reality of a business that out of lack of employment of the people but later turned a source of livelihood and wealth for the people of the region. Secondary sources of data were derived from relevant books, journal articles, and internet materials, focusing on indigenous African economies through aluminium foundry and pot making in Saki. The subtopic discusses the focus of this research.

3.1 Markets, marketing and patronage^{viii}

Markets, in the pre-colonial period, were an indispensable centre for the exchange of all articles of trade. The earliest literary evidence of the first half of the nineteenth century clearly shows that markets were conspicuous features of Yorubaland long before the colonial period (Okunade 2022). According to Hodder (1965, 97), markets, in the sense of public gatherings of buyers and sellers meeting at appointed places at regular intervals, are important elements of the social and economic landscape in Yorubaland and many African communities. The most prominent market in Saki in the postcolonial period is the Sango market, also known as Oja Owode (Owode market), which is known to have long existed. This market attracts patronage from all over Nigeria and beyond. Many came from Francophone countries, and others from northern Nigeria and many other places, both to sell their products and to purchase commodities from the market at their base. Aluminium pots are major products people patronise in this market, among other products.

Other crafts, especially aluminium pots, are local crafts that are known and conspicuously appreciated in the present-day markets. Aluminium pot making is a modern craft whose

products are thriving in the markets. The products which include cooking wares and utensils of various sizes are well known and patronised by a good number of buyers, especially in the western part of this country. In a nutshell, they are used in homes for cooking. Even with the advent of modern machine-made aluminium kitchen utensils that come in different sizes and attractive designs, the patronage of locally produced or moulded pots is still very high due to their retentive qualities. These aluminium pots are very strong and can be used either on local or kerosene stoves without leakage. They are cheaper than the modern machine-made ones. So, when a customer buys these locally produced ones, he or she saves a lot of money that can be used for other important purposes. At times several groups of associations, mostly the women's associations, are always known for the habit of patronizing these people with the sole aim of using them as a present to a celebrity during a celebration or anniversaries. At times, they distribute them to the people who are present during that occasion.^{ix}

Just as these local wares are available in Sango/Owode market in Saki, various other markets within Saki, in Oke-Ogun, Oyo State and Nigeria and the world at large trade in these local crafts, especially aluminium pots. For instance, these pots are found in Ibadan markets like Bere Oje, Oja Oba, Alesinloye and so on. A respondent from Lagos said, “I sell my market (*Ikoko irin*) at Oja Ile Epo, located around Iyana Opoja, and people do sell *Ikoko irin* at Ojota too and many other places.”^x This source offers more extensive information about this area:

I live in Ilorin and I sell (*Ikoko irin*) at Adifa market at Oja Oba in Ilorin. People patronise me from Kishi, Offa, Omuaran, Igbeti, Igbaja, Kannji and from Kogi State. They also sell *Ikoko irin* at Oja-Tuntun, in Ilorin. The number of sellers at Oja Tuntun cannot be compared to Adifa market because Adifa is larger in the sale of *Ikoko irin*.^{xi}

Aluminium pots from Saki are part of the features of all the aforementioned markets. Saki has become so distinctive in the production of aluminium pots, which have spread all over the world. People patronise Saki pots because they are aware that Saki is the home of quality and durable aluminium pot making. Baba Matthew Ogunrinde sheds more light on the importance of inscribing Saki on the pots, thus: “Some people went to Lagos and they could not sell their pots until they came back and wrote Saki on it.”^{xii} In other words, people refused to patronise their pots because there was no inscription, ‘Saki’, labelled on the pots. It is felt that once Saki is not written on it, it must be sub-standard pots which will not attract the interest of the people to purchase it.

3.2 Aluminium pot as an indicator of saki's popularity and wealth

As indicated above, aluminium pots have become a major source of income and one of the reasons for Saki's popularity, considering that the pots are trade-marked Saki and that the pots are sold in different places both in Nigeria and overseas. Many of the producers have also become so enriched by the sales of the products. Almost all the respondents interviewed in Saki and beyond agreed that *Ikoko irin* business has enhanced and boosted Saki's popularity and wealth. Many people in the world have known the town through the name written on the iron pots. Alhaji Musa Onikokorin in an interview said that "*ise ikoko irin gbe Saki laruge* (Aluminium pots making has enhanced the popularity of Saki). It has contributed to Saki's popularity. Everywhere you will see the traces of these pots, and Saki is always written on them.^{xiii} A respondent stated thus regarding the coverage of the sale of *Ikoko irin*:

I cannot explain the reach of our markets when it comes to aluminium pots because there are many. People patronise us from all parts of the world, even from London. Last week, some people still called from London via WhatsApp that they wanted *Ikoko irin*, and we did it for them. People from French countries also patronised us, including buyers within Nigeria such as Ibadan, Lagos, Akure and so on. These people value Saki's pots immensely. This has enhanced and enabled Saki to be popular because Saki is always written on the pots.^{xiv}

The *Ikoko irin* business has added grandeur and glory to Saki, as noted by all the respondents interviewed in Saki. Patronage extended to all parts of the world. An indication that it is not a mere local pot is being suggested in the declaration of one of the respondents that requests were made from London and supplies were made to the taste of the buyers. So, it is not an article restricted to a local environment, it is accessible to everyone in Nigeria and overseas.

3.3 Aluminium pot making and its socio-economic importance to Saki

It is no longer news that foundry and aluminium pot making in Saki is already an established trade that has attracted both local and international attention, and many who have chosen it as an occupation have their wealth attributed to it. So, the importance of the production of aluminium pots in Saki cannot be underplayed as it has spectacular effects on the economic and socio-cultural lives of the people. Through the business of aluminium pots, many people, from far and near, regularly patronise the popular weekly Owode market in Saki every Thursday.^{xv} They bring different articles and commodities to sell after which they also buy aluminium pots to sell in their different locations within Oke-Ogun, Nigeria and beyond. Aluminium pot makers in the town attracted wealth because of the heavy patronage of their products. In other words, Adeleke argues that this kind of system introduces a unique trading pattern in which the capital generated by the

outsiders is used in purchasing aluminium pots, thus generating income for the people of the town. Without gainsaying, some have become millionaires due to their trading in aluminium products.^{xvi} Many people are delighted about using aluminium pots from Saki, most especially housewives and caterers, because of their quality, durability, and multi-purpose functions. Hardly is there any woman worth her salt within the area and outside of it who does not have one of the sizes of the aluminium pots. For those who do not have, they usually rent or borrow if they have any event that would involve cooking for a large crowd.^{xvii} Mrs Adenike, a wholeseller of *Ikoko irin* in Saki, testified thus:

We sell quality local Saki iron pots, 10–15-year guarantee. All our locally made traditional pots, commonly called *Ikoko irin* are of the best quality, affordable, durable and very thick, and you have the chance to engrave or write your name on them. You cannot get the quality elsewhere unless Saki.^{xviii}

Just as these pots have become popular for their utilitarian values, they have also created wealth for those who mould them and even those who came to purchase them on commercial grounds. This is exemplified in the life of one of the icons in the business, the late Alhaji Taju Oya who was renowned for possessing several landed properties which he got from the proceeds of the craft. In addition, the production of aluminium pots has made Saki a prominent centre of production, learning and trade which has boosted the economy of the town.^{xix} This trade has immensely contributed to the economy of Saki. This is because different people in Nigeria and foreigners usually come around to buy these pots and those who are not directly involved in the iron pots business also benefit from it because some of the buyers usually buy other commodities along with iron pots.^{xx}

The social effect of the production of aluminium pots in Saki include migration into the land and a mix of cultures and inter-marriages between the people of the town and neighbouring states and countries such as Togo, Benin, Niger, Mali, and Burkina Faso. It has led to cross-cultural integration between and among the people and foreigners. Individuals or groups who developed an interest in this craft left their place of abode to learn and eventually settled in Saki because they had adapted to the culture and traditions of their host town. Another social effect is a more developed and civilised transportation system within and around Saki because neighbouring towns and countries engaged in coming down to the town to carry already-made aluminium pots for sale in their territory. Iron pot production has encouraged cultural diffusion. This is because migrations occur at different times, as well as the exchange of cultures. The coming together of people made interaction possible with their neighbours, and as such, copying another's activities became inevitable. This was the case in the production of iron pots in Saki. For instance, the mode of dressing is one of the cultural diffusions. The aluminium pot has become a commercial symbol of Saki and a household item in the locality and beyond. Its energy

efficiency, durability, and effectiveness for all forms of cooking have given aluminium pots a comparative advantage over imported pots. Given its economic importance, it has in the last two decades attracted high demand from the neighbouring West African countries like Benin, Togo, Burkina Faso, and Niger Republics to boost export trade.^{xxi} A respondent said thus: People from all over the world came around to buy the pots; it is not limited to Saki indigenes alone. People come from Ibadan, Ilorin, Lagos, Igbeti, and even from the French land. This is because since Saki started doing it, the business was not effectively functioning again in French land, so they usually came to Saki to purchase it to sell in their land. This is because Saki knows how to do it better.^{xxii}

Saki has been undergoing rapid developments and a higher growth rate due to the level of the commercial activities regarding the production of aluminium pots primarily in wholesale and retail forms (Siyabola, *et al*, 2012). Aluminium pot making has become a hallmark of Saki and it is known virtually all-over West Africa, African and beyond. For instance, corroborating the respondent's view above, this individual posits that:

I have customers from all over, such as Benin, Jos, Lagos, and even from Frenchland. I supply them because they bought it in commercial quantities. It is a good business, and I am a distributor. I started this business around 1992, and the business has continued to thrive since then. It is good and it attracts good markets.^{xxiii}

A respondent also noted that Saki's expertise in making iron pots surpassed any town around it. In different places, such as Ilorin, Lagos and so on, they will say it's Saki's pot that they want.^{xxiv} Local crafts are generally appreciated in the present-day market. Likewise, the local cast aluminium pot making is a modern craft whose products are thriving in the markets. The products, which include cooking wares and utensils of various sizes, are well known and patronised by a good number of buyers, especially in the western part of this country. They are used in homes for cooking. Even with the advent of modern machine-made aluminium kitchen utensils that come in different sizes and attractive designs, the patronage of locally produced or moulded pots is still very high due to their retentive qualities.^{xxv} The use of local utensils will be perpetuated because some local people cannot afford the modernised ones. Besides, the aluminium pots are of high quality and durability, so there is no reason to bother buying the costly ones since they will serve the same purpose. Locally produced ones save lots of money that could be channelled to other important purposes.

Considering the quality of these pots, their utilitarian values cut across different homes and they have one advantage when these pots are old or damaged, they can be sold as scraps to the producers for recycling, or a user can give half of the amount for the old or

damaged pot in exchange for a brand new one.^{xxvi} This has some economic advantages, as the value can still be placed on the old one because it can be used again. Ceremonies are another important way the pots are used. At times, groups or associations, mostly women's associations, always patronise the aluminium pot makers with the sole aim of using it as a present to a celebrity during a celebration or anniversary. They distribute them to the members of their associations present at such occasions. Instead of buying modern items like coolers and umbrellas, people choose local products, such as aluminium pots and this in turn creates more awareness of the pots.

4. CONCLUSION

Saki as a notable commercial hub for foundry products, has over the years engaged in aluminium pots, which are known in Nigeria and beyond. Tracing its early beginnings to the late 1960s, the Saki people demonstrated unusual expertise and special abilities in aluminium pot making. The business owners produce strong and durable pots of different sizes with a trade mark, '*Saki*', written on it, sold within, and exported abroad, thus achieving wealth through the business. Aluminium pot making has become an established trade in Saki, and it has promoted and boosted the economy of Saki, thus contributing immensely to Saki's popularity and fame. Many people visit Saki for commercial purposes, and top on their priority is to engage in trade in the business of aluminium pots, which has improved Saki's economy. The industries have significantly contributed to the local economy and provided sustainable livelihoods for numerous individuals and families within the community, serving as important sources of income and employment. It is altogether constructive to argue that the trade has contributed to all aspects of Saki's life, be it economic and socio-cultural aspects. It can therefore be established that the trade of aluminium pot making has immensely and significantly contributed to the popularity, reputation, and wealth of Saki. This study in essence, contributes to a deeper understanding of indigenous African economies and underscores the importance of preserving traditional craftsmanship and cultural continuity in contemporary African societies.

END NOTES

- ⁱ Interview with Papa Matthew Ogunrinde, Saki Toro, 68 years, 22/10/2016. This man was the one of the earliest individuals who learned the business in Saki and practiced in Saki till old age.
- ⁱⁱ Interview with Papa Matthew Ogunrinde, Saki Toro, 68 years, 22/10/2016.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Mariam Adeleke's interview with Tiamiyu Ayinla, 75 years, Aluminium pot maker, Pakanyin, Saki, 25/05/2013.
- ^{iv} Mariam Adeleke's interview with Tiamiyu Ayinla, 75 years, Aluminium pot maker, Pakanyin, Saki, 25/05/2013.
- ^v Interview with A.A. Kolajo, Ibadan, 84 years, 14/03/2017.
- ^{vi} National Centre for Technology Management (NACETEM). Indigenous technology mapping and analysis of skills acquisition methodologies in the aluminium and bronze casting industry in Nigeria. Policy Research Project Funded by the Federal Government of Nigeria, 2008.
- ^{vii} National Centre for Technology Management (NACE- TEM), "Indigenous Technology Mapping and Analysis of Skills Acquisition Methodologies in the Aluminium and Bronze Casting Industry in Nigeria," Policy Research Project Funded by the Federal Government of Nigeria, 2008).
- ^{viii}
- ^{ix} Adeleke Mariam Mojisola, Production of Aluminium Pots (*Ikoko Irin*) in Saki, 1969-2000, unpublished dissertation, April, 2014, p. 50.
- ^x Interview with Mummy Yusuf, 40+, Lagos, 15/06/2022.
- ^{xi} Interview with Mummy Laide, 40+, Ilorin, 15/06/2022.
- ^{xii} Interview with Papa Matthew Ogunrinde, Saki Toro, 68 years, 22/10/2016.
- ^{xiii} Interview with Alhaji Musa Onikokorin, 63 years, Ayetoro, Saki, 24/05/2022.
- ^{xiv} Interview with Iya Photo, Saki, 13/05/2022.
- ^{xv} My grandma, Mama Alice Omolola Okunade, sold Locust bean and shea butter at the market for more than five decades before she could not go out again.
- ^{xvi} Adeleke Mariam Mojisola, Production of Aluminium Pots (*Ikoko Irin*) in Saki, 1969-2000, unpublished dissertation, April 2014, p. 41.
- ^{xvii} I witnessed this as an indigene when I was in Saki. I had my primary and secondary education in Saki.
- ^{xviii} Mrs Adenike, <https://jiji.ng/saki-west/kitchen-and-dining/saki-iron-pots-ikoko-irin-vW3Z8m176nX6TQD78gxjleP2.html> assessed 06/06/2022.
- ^{xix} Adeleke Mariam Mojisola, Production of Aluminium Pots (*Ikoko Irin*) in Saki, 1969-2000, unpublished dissertation, April 2014, p. 41.
- ^{xx} Interview with Alhaji Musa Onikokorin, 63 years, Ayetoro, Saki, 24/05/2022
- ^{xxi} Adeleke Mariam Mojisola, Production of Aluminium Pots (*Ikoko Irin*) in Saki, 1969-2000, unpublished dissertation, April 2014, p. 41.
- ^{xxii} Interview with Alhaji Musa Onikokorin, 63 years, Ayetoro, Saki, 24/05/2022.
- ^{xxiii} Interview with Mrs Moranro, Iganran, Saki, 58 years, 16/03/2017.
- ^{xxiv} Interview with Mrs Moranro, Iganran, Saki, 58 years, 16/03/2017.
- ^{xxv} <http://timopd1.blogspot.com/2010/07/indigenius-aluminum-casting-in-nigeria.html>, Indigenous Aluminium Casting in Nigeria, Friday, July 16, 2010 assessed 25/05/2022
- ^{xxvi} <http://timopd1.blogspot.com/2010/07/indigenius-aluminum-casting-in-nigeria.html>, Indigenous Aluminium Casting in Nigeria, Friday, July 16, 2010 assessed 25/05/2022

REFERENCES

- Adelabu, O. S., and A. D. Campbell. 2020. Evaluation of Indigenous Technology for Cast Aluminium Cookware Production in Nigeria: A Case Study of User Health Risks from Cookware Made in Saki. In *9th International Conference on Appropriate Technology*.
- Andah, B. W. 1992. *Nigeria's Indigenous Technology*, Ibadan: Ibadan University Press.
- Diboye-Suku, Z. A. and Onuoha. 2019. Developing Indigenous Technology for Sustainability in the Manufacturing Sector of Nigeria, *International Journal of Business School Annals*, 6(1), 13-19.
- Hodder, B. W. 1965. Some comments on the origins of traditional markets in Africa south of the Sahara. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 97-105.
- Jain, R.K. 2006. *Production Technology*, Delhi: Khanna Publishers.
- Kpelou P, Mouzou E, Aminti E, Kongnine, D. M., 2021. Microstructural and Physicochemical Properties of Some Aluminum Cooking Tools Obtained by Artisanal Recycling, *European Journal Of Materials Science And Engineering*, 6(3), 148-156.
- National Centre for Technology Management (NACETEM). Indigenous technology mapping and analysis of skills acquisition methodologies in the aluminium and bronze casting industry in Nigeria. Policy Research Project Funded by the Federal Government of Nigeria, 2008.
- Okpoko, A. I. 1999. *African Indigenous Technology: With Particular Reference to Nigeria*, Ibadan: Wisdom Publishers Limited.
- Okunade, S.A. 2022. "Reading Indigenous African Economies Through Production and Exchange: Pre-colonial Yorubaland and Articles of Trade*", Fiorito, L., Scheall, S. and Suprinyak, C.E. (Ed.) *Research in the History of Economic Thought and Methodology: Including a Symposium on David Gordon: American Radical Economist (Research in the History of Economic Thought and Methodology, Vol. 40A)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Bingley.
- Pacey, A. 2001. "Meaning in technology." 243.
- Siyanbola, W. O., Egbetokun, A. A., Oluseyi, I., Olamide, O. O., Aderemi, H. O., & Sanni, M. 2012^{xxvi}. Indigenous technologies and innovation in Nigeria: opportunities for SMEs, *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*.